

INFLUENCE OF USING GAMES ON ENGLISH LESSONS.

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ABSTRACT: This article describes the influence of using games on English classes.

There are many ways to introduce English for school students. One of them is by means of games. For that reason, research work describes new modern technology for classroom.

KEY WORDS: special skills, communication, aggressive, motivate, good loser, modern teaching methods.

At different periods of time teaching a foreign language caused a lot of problems concerning the methods and ways of teaching English in particular. There appeared methods of teaching bearing various names and having numerous aims and purposes. There were traditional methods used for many years and they were quite appropriate for those times. About 20-25 years ago there appeared modern and contemporary methods of teaching English which have changed almost completely both the methods and methodology of teaching English.

Having mastered English, people can communicate with other people, especially with foreign people easily, and it can reduce misunderstanding in communication. Teaching school students English is not so simple because English is not their native language, and it is a new thing for them. Interest of students to studying English is as a key which simplifies their development of English. The teacher has to have good and interesting equipment to teach English in order to make young pupils interested and motivated to learn English.

There are many ways to introduce English for school students. One of them is by means of games. As all of us know that children like to play so by means of games as a teaching method students can be more interested in learning English. Games can be used not only for an entertainment, but also for motivation of students to master English easily and quickly. Training at practice is a good way to make them easily understand about English because with doing amusing actions, they will find it easy to remember and to learn material which is taught by the teacher.

Games and fun activities are a vital part of teaching English as a foreign language. Whether you're teaching adults or children, games will liven up your lesson and ensure that your students will leave the classroom wanting more.

Games can be used to warm up the class before your lesson begins, during the lesson to give students a break when you're tackling a tough subject, or at the end of class when you have a few minutes left to kill. Teaching English is a hard work. When we speak about teaching English it is difficult work for teachers and students. Interest in studying English steadily grows in recent years. For the correct teaching of grammar, it is necessary representing special skills. To help children to study and develop skills of conversation becomes more important, than just to learn language. Nevertheless, the teaching process shouldn't be difficult or painful. Teachers can teach English grammar in an amusing way. There was a movement from traditional methods of teaching English grammar by writing, copying and worksheets to more active approach – teaching grammar by means of games. Researchers also began to study it as these new methods work.

Harmer J. and Essen Metin continue explaining that teaching grammar using games helps children not only to gain knowledge, but also to be able to apply and use this knowledge. They say: "Games and problem-solving activities, which are task-based and have a purpose beyond the production of correct speech, are the examples of the most preferable communicative activities." [16,15]. As games motivate students, perhaps, it is the best reason, according to Harmer and Metin to use games at the lessons "the use of such activities both increases the cooperation and competition in the classroom." It is possible to use games to lessen nervousness through the competition or games which create closer connection between students and the teacher.

The other researcher shows that games help and to encourage many pupils to maintain their interest and work. Games in language class help pupils to see how studying of English is pleasant and useful. Playing games in class develops ability to communicate in cooperation without being aggressive and to be "a good loser".

Games also help teachers to create conditions in which their language is useful and significant. Pupils want to take part and to make very much to understand what is told by others, or was written, and they have to speak or write to express their own point of view or to give information.

Besides, games have advantage that allows students to practice and to analyze lexicon, grammar and structure widely. They can make it because

students are often more motivated to play games, than work at a table. Besides, during games students are concentrated on activity and finally absorb language subconsciously. It is also possible to add that cheerful training games, as a rule, contain repetition which allows the language to stick.

The last concern of teachers of a foreign language is that using games they teach their pupils to communicate. After realization of communicative competence, activity or methods which are purposeful and which direct children to use of language inventively have gained meaning. Games are problem solving activities which are task-based are also intended, besides production of the exact speech examples is more preferable in communicative activity.

Such activities emphasize not only competence, but also productivity of teaching process. Nevertheless, they are integral parts of grammar lessons as they strengthen a match form of discourse. In such activity attention is paid to discourse context.

Both games and problem solving activities have a similar aim. Games are held according to rules, and they are pleasant. The majority of games demand choral answers or group work while problem solving activities demand individual reaction and creative decisions. Games and problem solving activities are, as a rule, used after the presentation, in practical part such as communicative tasks that can be processed only after development sufficient grammar and lexical points. Thanks to well-planned games, pupils can in practice acquire lexicon, grammar and structures widely. Playing games increases motivation of pupils. They also reduce tension in class. At the same time, when pupils play games, attention of pupils is on them not on language

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